

Spectroscopic and Kinetic Studies on the Transformation of Charge Transfer Complexes with Alicyclic N-Donors

U. MURALIKRISHNA*, Y. V. S. K. SESHASAYI and MANNAM KRISHNAMURTHY

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

Manuscript received 7 May 1983, accepted 12 September 1983

The transformation of charge transfer (CT) complexes of 2,3,5,6-tetrabromo-1,4-benzoquinone with three alicyclic N-donors, piperidine, piperazine and morpholine, in chloroform has been reported. The transformation leads to the formation of substitution products in solution. The solid products have been isolated and characterised as diaminodibromo-1,4-benzoquinones by ir, ¹H-nmr and elemental analysis. The results on the kinetics of the formation of products indicate that the rate is first order both with the acceptor and donor. An intermediate between CT and product has been postulated and a mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed. The reactivities of the donors are found in the order piperidine > piperazine > morpholine. The influences of the dielectric constant of the solvent, and temperature have been studied and thermodynamic parameters for the formation of products have been computed.

SYSTEMATIC studies involving the interaction of benzoquinones with amines are limited¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our studies on the formation of charge transfer (CT) complexes with three alicyclic-N-donors⁵, piperidine (PD), piperazine (PZ) and morpholine (ML), we now report the spectroscopic and kinetic investigations on the transformation of CT complexes to final products in chloroform, using 2,3,5,6-tetrabromo-1,4-benzoquinone (bromanil) as electron acceptor.

Experimental

Chemicals and solutions: Bromanil was prepared and purified as mentioned earlier⁵ and a stock solution (5×10^{-3} M) was prepared, protected from light and used as and when needed. PD and ML were purified by distillation and PZ by sublimation. Stock solutions (each 5×10^{-3} M) were prepared and diluted as needed. Chloroform, special for spectroscopy, was further purified⁶. All other reagents and solvents were sufficiently pure.

Instruments: A Pye Unicam SP-700 A-UV-VIS spectrophotometer was used for recording the time dependent absorption spectra and CZ Spekol (with EK 5) spectrocoulometer for absorption measurements using optically matched cells of 1 cm path. Temperature was maintained constant at the desired value by circulating water using a Toshniwal GL-15 constant temperature bath. Beckman IR-12 and

Brucker FT-400 MHz NMR spectrometers were used for the spectral data.

Isolation of solid products: About 0.5 g bromanil in chloroform was treated with 3-5 times excess of the donor. The mixture was refluxed for completion of the reaction. The unreacted donor was separated by fractionation by column chromatography using 1:1 *n*-hexane-benzene mixture as eluent. The solid products were isolated by evaporating the solvent mixture and dried.

Kinetic measurements: Bromanil and donor were mixed with chloroform in a 10 ml flask, with the donor in far excess. The absorbance was measured at different times at the λ_{\max} values in the visible region of the products (Table 1) and the pseudo first order rate constants (k') were calculated from the gradients of $\ln (A_{\infty} - A_t)$ against time plots. Dielectric constant (ϵ) was varied by mixing chloroform with appropriate volumes of carbon tetrachloride (for low ϵ) and 1,2-dichloroethane (for high ϵ). The effect of variation of temperature was studied by circulating water at different temperatures.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The composition of the CT complexes formed between bromanil and donors⁵ is 1:1 and these complexes are stable in presence of high concentrations of bromanil (Fig. 1). In presence of high concentrations of donors these blue coloured complexes transform to yellow colour in solution. The time dependent absorption spectra for bromanil-PD system are recorded in Fig. 2. The products in each system have two absorption maxima, one in the visible and the other in the uv region (Table 1).

* Author for correspondence, presently Department of Chemistry, A.U.P.G.E. Centre, Nuzvid-521 201.

Fig. 1. Mole ratio plot for bromanil and PD.
 $[PD] = 4 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Fig. 2. Time dependent absorption spectra.
 $[Bromanil] = 2 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[PD] = 8 \times 10^{-3} M$, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 are the spectra recorded with donor blank, 1, 4, 10, 30 and 60 min, after mixing the components in chloroform.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF THE PRODUCTS

Donor	λ_{max} , nm
PD	451, 198
PZ	449, 230
ML	445, 247

Characterisation of transformed species: The yellow coloured solutions and the isolated products resulting after transformation have the same absorption characteristics.

The ir spectra of the products indicate most of the frequencies pertinent to the acceptor and donor moieties of the products (Table 2) are well in agreement with those reported earlier for halobenzoquinones⁷, PD^{8,9}, PZ¹⁰ and ML⁸. The absence of N-H stretching frequency at $\sim 3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ further indicates the loss of proton on nitrogen of the donor moiety. In case of PZ, the observed 3210 cm^{-1} is due to the presence of the other N-H not involved in the substitution.

TABLE 2—IR DATA OF THE PRODUCTS

with PD cm^{-1}	with PZ cm^{-1}	with ML cm^{-1}	Assignments/ Functional group
—	3210	—	Aliphatic N-H
2940	2915	2945	Aliphatic C-H
2850	2835	2855	
1645	1640	1645	Carbonyl
1550	1545	1565	-C=O-
1400	1390	1400	-O-N-
1360	1355	1355	-O-C-
1340	1330	1335	
1285	1265	1275	Ar-N-C
—	—	1160	-O-O-C-
1045	1040	1060	-C-Br
845	840	850	-O-C-O-
785	720	735	
—	—	610	-O-O-C-

The $^1\text{H-nmr}$ spectra (Table 3) also indicate the absence of N-H proton¹¹ (in case of PZ and ML only nitrogen is the donation site, though the donor is twin-site), and visualises the possibility of the substitution type of reaction.

TABLE 3— $^1\text{H-NMR}$ OF THE DONORS AND PRODUCTS
 (TMS as internal standard)

Donor	Proton resonance (no. of protons)		
	on N	on αC to N	on β , γC to N
PD	2.08 (1)	2.65 (4)	1.51 (6)
Product ⁺	absent	3.38 (8)	1.67 (12)
PZ ⁺	2.02 (2)	2.66 (8)	
Product ⁺	2.52 (2)	2.42 (8)	1.69 (8)
ML	1.68 (1)	3.50 (4)	2.74 (4)
Product ⁺	absent	3.76 (8)	3.52 (8)

*in CDCl_3 .

That the substitution¹² has taken place is further corroborated by testing for the presence of free bromide ion by the usual silver bromide test. Elemental analysis (Table 4) confirms the products as diaminodibromo-1,4-benzoquinones.

Kinetics on the formation of products: The salient features of the present kinetic study (Table 5) are as follows:

The reaction is first order with respect to bromanil and donor and total order is two.

TABLE 4—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS

Product with	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen
PD	44.36 (44.44)	4.74 (4.63)	6.42 (6.48)
PZ	38.80 (38.73)	4.18 (4.16)	12.8 (12.9)
ML	38.42 (38.53)	3.76 (3.67)	6.36 (6.42)

From the results, the rate law may be written as

$$d(\text{product})/dt = k[\text{CT}]_0[\text{D}] \quad \dots (1)$$

As the donor is isolated

$$[\text{bromanil}]_0 = [\text{CT}]_0 \quad \dots (2)$$

From the above two equations

$$d(\text{product})/dt = k[\text{bromanil}]_0[\text{D}]_0 \quad \dots (3)$$

This equation represents the observed results.

TABLE 5—KINETIC RESULTS ON THE FORMATION OF PRODUCTS (Temperature 303K)

$10^4[\text{Bromanil}]$ <i>M</i>	$10^4[\text{Donor}]$ <i>M</i>	ϵ	$10^4 k'$ sec^{-1}	$10^4 k''$ $M^{-1}\text{sec}^{-1}$
with PD				
3.00	1.29	4.8	2.20	
4.00	1.29	4.8	2.17	
6.00	1.29	4.8	2.19	
5.00	1.29	4.8	2.17	16.9
5.00	1.03	4.8	1.73	16.8
5.00	1.54	4.8	2.64	17.1
5.00	2.06	4.8	3.52	17.1
4.00	1.31	3.3		6.3
4.00	1.31	4.0		9.4
4.00	1.31	6.4		21.3
4.00	1.31	8.0		27.4
with PZ				
3.20	1.58	4.8	0.95	
5.62	1.58	4.8	0.96	
6.42	1.58	4.8	0.95	
4.01	1.58	4.8	0.94	6.0
4.01	1.06	4.8	0.63	6.0
4.01	1.33	4.8	0.79	6.0
4.01	2.11	4.8	1.28	6.1
5.02	3.03	3.6		4.8
5.02	3.03	5.6		7.7
5.02	3.03	7.2		10.8
with ML				
3.00	30.4	4.8	1.55	
6.00	30.4	4.8	1.54	
7.00	30.4	4.8	1.57	
5.00	30.4	4.8	1.54	0.51
5.00	20.2	4.8	1.01	0.50
5.00	35.2	4.8	1.83	0.52
5.00	45.2	4.8	2.25	0.50
6.00	34.3	3.0		0.39
6.00	34.3	4.0		0.47
6.00	34.3	6.4		0.79
6.00	34.3	7.5		0.99
6.00	34.3	8.2		1.09

According to Nagakura *et al*¹ the electron donor-acceptor interaction between quinone as

acceptor (A) and amine as donor (D) may be represented as

or

From the [product] vs time curves¹, the observed initial quadratic behaviour (Fig. 3) supports the presence of an intermediate between CT complex and substitution product. The CT complex formed is stable in 1:1 composition and will transform only in presence of excess donor.

Fig. 3. Time vs absorbance plots for the product formation. [Bromanil] = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$; A, B and C with [PD] = $1.3 \times 10^{-3} M$, [PZ] = $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ and [ML] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, respectively.

No spectral evidence could be obtained for the intermediate because of its transitory existence. However, the kinetics on the transformation of CT complex for bromanil-PD system results in the bimolecular rate constant (k'') = 0.7, as against k' for the formation of CT and product (9.3^{18} and $1.7 \text{ lit mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, respectively).

Mechanism: In view of the above, the following mechanism may be proposed for the electron donor-acceptor interaction between alicyclic-N-donors and bromanil

The results (k'' 's) further indicate that the rate of the reaction is in the order PD > PZ > ML.

Effect of variation of dielectric constant (ϵ) and temperature: The rate of the reaction is found

linearly dependent on the ϵ (Table 5). From the temperature variation study the thermodynamic parameters have been calculated and computed in Table 6. The energy (E_a), enthalpy (ΔH^*) and free energy (ΔG^*) of activation are in the order

Donor	E_a k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* e.u.	ΔG^* k cal mol ⁻¹
PD	4.75	4.16	-47.8	18.5
PZ	7.47	6.88	-46.9	19.1
ML	7.68	7.03	-45.3	20.6

PD < PZ < ML, indicating that the reaction can more easily be brought in the reverse order, which correlates the reactivities of the donors. The reactivities of the donors also obey the trend in their pK_a values, PD (11.1) > PZ (9.7) > ML (8.5).

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (Y.V.S.K.S. and M.K.) are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Senior Research Fellowships.

References

1. T. NOGAMI, K. YOSHIHARA, H. HOSOYA and S. NAGAKURA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 2670.
2. W. J. LAUTENBERGER and J. G. MILLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 2722.
3. P. C. DWIVEDI and A. K. BANGA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 1768.
4. U. MURALIKRISHNA and M. KRISHNAMURTHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, **21A**, 1018.
5. U. MURALIKRISHNA, Y. V. S. K. SESHASAYI and M. KRISHNAMURTHY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 447.
6. A. WEISSBERGER, "Technique of Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1955, Vol. VII.
7. G. B. BARUAH, S. N. SINGH and M. G. JAYASWAL, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1969, **7**, 280.
8. K. WALLENFELS and W. DRABER, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 1889.
9. D. VEDAL, O. H. ELLESTAD, P. KLABOE and G. HAGEN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1976, **32A**, 877.
10. P. J. HENDRA and D. B. POWELL, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 299.
11. S. DAHNE, J. RANFT and H. PAUL, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1964, 3355.
12. B. K. DAS and B. MAJER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 1055.
13. U. MURALIKRISHNA, Y. V. S. K. SESHASAYI and M. KRISHNAMURTHY, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, in press.